

Children's Spontaneity in an Orff-Schulwerk Classroom: A Qualitative Study

34

MARTINA VASIL is a Music Education doctoral candidate at West Virginia University, Morgantown, WV, where she also earned her bachelor's. She earned her MA from Eastman School of Music, Rochester, NY. Martina taught K–8 general music and band for six years in Pittsburgh, PA, and is certified in all levels of Orff teacher education. She was a local conference chair for the 2011 AOSA national conference and will present at the 2014 conference. Currently, she is president of the Pittsburgh Golden Triangle Chapter of AOSA.

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to explore children's spontaneity in a formal educational music setting, specifically an Orff-Schulwerk classroom. The research centered on two questions: (a) what are the spontaneous responses of children in an Orff-Schulwerk music class, and (b) to what extent does the music teacher encourage or discourage these behaviors? Participants were two kindergarten classes, two first-grade classes, one second-grade class, and the music teacher. Data were collected from four observations over a five-week period. Results indicate that children's spontaneous responses were rhythmic, melodic, spoken, and exploratory, and that the music teacher encouraged spontaneous responses by offering students choices, asking open-ended questions, and providing a safe classroom environment. Understanding and encouraging children's spontaneous responses in a music classroom provides more effective and relevant instruction, and helps children become independent thinkers and musicians.

By Martina Vasil

Under the Orff-Schulwerk approach, many teachers use the words *creative*, *improvisatory*, and *spontaneous* to describe children's music making and play. They may be unaware that these terms describe specific activities in the music classroom.

- *Creativity* is the quality of being able to create, rather than imitate (Merriam-Webster, 2012). When children create, they manipulate objects or ideas in new forms or ways.

- *Improvisation* means impromptu composing, reciting, arranging, making, or playing (Merriam-Webster, 2012). When improvising, a child controls the creation from start to finish. According to Curran (2006), this is a “highly specialized artistic behavior” (Curran, 2006, p. 487).
- *Spontaneity* can be a voluntary or involuntary action or movement (Merriam-Webster, 2012). Unlike creativity and improvisation, spontaneity is a first, natural reaction to a stimulus. It is a more elemental level of musical consciousness (Curran, 2006).

Various studies have investigated spontaneous musical responses of preschool age children, especially in free-play settings (Barrett, 2006; Moog, 1976; Sims, 1985; Young, 2002). These spontaneous musical responses can be divided into two categories: spontaneous movements and singing.

For spontaneous movements, Sims (1985) conducted a study in a highly controlled setting. Three-, four-, and five-year olds were individually placed in a room with a researcher and asked to move to music. The researcher found that three-year-olds did not move 50% of the time; five-year-olds responded with a high percentage of locomotor movements. Rhythmic movement of four- and five-year-olds was similar and over three times as much as that of three-year-olds. However, three-year-olds reacted faster to initial changes in the music. Sims suggested that it might be appropriate to group preschool children by age, in particular separating three- and five-year-olds, for creative movement activities (1985).

From observing two- to four-year-old children's spontaneous singing behavior, Moog (1976) categorized the singing into three groups: *imaginative*, *narrative*, and *potpourri*. In imaginative songs, children sang freely, varying the melodic contour and focusing on the sound of their voices, rather than creating meaningful lyrics. In narrative songs, children varied the melody and lyrics, often including nonsense words and fragments of familiar songs. Potpourri songs were known songs interspersed with original melodic and lyric devices.

Young (2002) defined spontaneous vocalizations as “a broad range of vocal behaviors including all kinds of singing and playful vocalizations” (p. 43), which excluded spoken words. She discovered that children's spontaneous vocalizations were richly expressive and imaginative; she suggested that adults

encourage and interact with children as they play, rather than restrict or curb children's activities.

Barrett (2006) found that young children's invented song evolves from their early musical interactions with others, reflects their capacity to create, and is fundamental to developing music-making creativity. Barrett revealed that spontaneous song emerges from 18 months to seven years, and then gradually disappears. Barrett attributed this to children entering a formal educational environment that does not value or encourage spontaneity.

Encouraging children to explore elemental music through improvisation and creative response is part of Orff Schulwerk's pedagogy (Shamrock, 1997). As Mead reminds us, “the children's world is one of sound making, movement, and play, and the use of their natural behaviors ensures learning” (1996, p. 40). Thus, it is important for Orff-Schulwerk teachers to pay careful attention to children's first and natural or spontaneous responses to musical stimuli, especially when delivering instruction in the classroom. By understanding children's natural spontaneous responses to music, teachers can be more responsive to students' interests and needs, and infuse their teaching with new, creative, and innovative ideas.

The purpose of this study was to explore children's spontaneity in a formal educational music setting, specifically in an Orff-Schulwerk classroom. Two research questions were posed: (a) what are the spontaneous responses of children in an Orff-Schulwerk music class, and (b) to what extent does the music teacher encourage or discourage this behavior?

Method

Data collection was conducted through four observations over a five-week period. Informal conversations and a formal interview were conducted with the music teacher during the data-collection period. The researcher collected artifacts (lesson plans, visual materials, and photographs) while observing the children. To capture children's spontaneous responses and gain insight into their learning context without affecting their responses, this researcher used non-participant observation (Campbell, 2010; Emerson, Fretz, & Shaw, 1995). While taking field notes, the researcher made a conscious effort to avoid personal bias and broaden and narrow the focus of attention, at times taking in the class as a whole and at other times focusing on one child (Emerson et al., 1995).

Participants

Participants in this study were divided into six units: two kindergarten classes, two first-grade classes, one second-grade class, and a music teacher. The observation took place at a public, mid-sized, K-5 elementary school located in the suburbs of a small northeastern U.S. city.

The students in these classes were predominantly Caucasian, with only 11% of minority populations (including African-American, Asian, and Hispanic). Most of the students were low-income, with 64% of students eligible for a discounted or free lunch. The music teacher had 16 years of elementary music teaching experience and was certified in the highest level of Orff Schulwerk. She verbally agreed to the study. Permission to observe children at the school was approved with a signed letter from the school's administration.

Analysis

The data gathered was first arranged chronologically, and then clustered into two different groups that addressed the research questions. Themes were identified and data triangulated among observation data, informal conversations, the formal interview, artifacts, and visual media (Leedy & Ormrod, 2013). The music teacher was sent a copy of the final manuscript to verify, revise, and approve the information.

Results: Children's Responses

The first question posed by this study was, "What are the spontaneous responses of children in an Orff-Schulwerk music class?" After analyzing the data, the researcher grouped children's spontaneous responses into rhythmic, melodic, spoken, and exploratory categories.

Rhythmic Responses

Many children in grades K-2 responded rhythmically to the teacher's instruction during music classes. When she directed kindergarten students to show the beat, they would swish their hands, tap their stomachs, take big steps, or dance on the pulse. They continued similar rhythmic behavior during pauses in instruction. When the teacher wrote on the board, music making continued as students rhythmically tapped non-pitched percussion instruments on their chins, stomachs, and the floor.

Instead of demonstrating the response that the teacher directed, a few children in kindergarten

and first grade tapped the rhythm of the words, played on specific words in a poem, or played an ostinato pattern. For example, when learning the song *Old King Glory* (Amidon & Amidon, 1991), kindergarteners were supposed to play their maracas on the beat as they sang. However, one child shook his maracas in an ostinato pattern: ♪♪♪♩. In first grade, the class was tracking the melody and singing the first part of each phrase in the song, *Raindrops, Raindrops* (Teacher Created Resources Staff, 2009). One boy was not doing the movements at all. Instead, he was lightly clapping the rhythm of the entire line: ♪♪♪♪ | ♪♪♪♩ (following the phrase, "Raindrops, raindrops, falling down").

Many children in grades K-1 expressed themselves spontaneously through steady beats. In a kindergarten listening lesson, the teacher asked students to identify objects suggested by the piece. Most students initially sat still as they listened, but several began to swing their arms and bounce on their knees to the beat. One boy patted his legs, and one girl did a snap-clap-patsch-clap pattern to the beat. By the end of the piece, most students were patsching the beat. In one of the first-grade classes, the teacher taught a folk dance in longways set where students sashayed up the middle. Most students spontaneously clapped to the beat without being told.

Children in second grade altered body percussion ostinati without teacher direction. For example, the teacher taught the children an ostinato pattern with a partner: "pat, pat, clap your neighbor" (♪♪♪♪). Some students patted each other's knees for the length of the ostinato, and two girls were not sitting down but were kneeling and performing the ostinato pattern.

Melodic Responses

Several children in kindergarten and second grade responded melodically to class instruction by singing an invented song, humming, or singing solfège patterns. One kindergartener sang an invented song after the class brainstormed various names of songs about rain; she sat up on her knees and her hands followed the descending melodic pattern that she sang, "Rain coming down from the clouds." Several children in kindergarten and second grade hummed the melody or melodic patterns from songs they had learned as they lined up at the end of music class.

In second grade, the class learned solfège patterns and imitated the teacher's Curwen hand signs.

continued on page 38

While many children tried to anticipate the solfège patterns, one child turned away from the class and experimented with different solfège patterns on his own.

Spoken Responses

A few children in kindergarten and first grade spoke in response to a variety of activities. Some discussed the music; one kindergartener said, "I'm listening for the beat" and another said, "It's a pattern!" In a timbre exploration activity, first graders imitated the teacher by rubbing and tapping on a hand drum to simulate the sounds of rain. A few students commented on what they heard, saying, for example, "That's a hard rain."

Some children in first grade improvised dialogue. For example, in a set dance, the students greeted each other "Nice to meet you" or "Hi, how are you?" For another first-grade lesson, the teacher prepared students for a movement activity by placing cards that had stick figures drawn on them in different places of the room. All of the children immediately gathered around the cards, with a few waving and saying "Hello!" to the stick figures.

Exploratory Responses

Kindergarteners varied in their reactions when holding non-pitched percussion instruments during instructional pauses or while waiting a turn to play. They held their hand drums at different angles against their bodies or held sticks in a variety of ways; some held them like they were about to start

Figure 1: Holding Drumsticks Like Making a Fire.

SOURCE: MARTINA VASIL.

a fire, some like they were a signaling soldier (one arm up and one arm down), and others made the letters "V" and "T." (See Figures 1 and 2.)

At the beginnings and ends of classes, kindergarteners exhibited natural movements. For example, a few students stomped into the music room. At the end of class, some students walked in lobster or eel movements that resembled an earlier class activity. One walked stiffly, like a robot.

First graders varied spontaneous movements through acting or dramatizing. When the teacher suggested several ways to move to a song about rain (e.g., opening umbrellas or jumping in puddles), most followed the suggestions. A few moved differently: one child skipped, another combined walking and twirling, one hopped in a small circle on one foot, and two girls held hands and simply walked.

First-grade children explored movement when learning set dances. Students stood in a long-ways set and the teacher instructed them to pretend like they were shaking someone's hand. Some students shook hands once, others energetically shook hands several times, and one child swung both hands as if holding a pretend sword.

Figure 2: Holding Drumsticks Like a Soldier.

SOURCE: MARTINA VASIL.

Results: Music Teacher Responses

The second question of the study was, “to what extent does the music teacher encourage or discourage this behavior?”

The study teacher appeared to encourage spontaneity. She viewed her teaching role as a facilitator who guided rather than led students towards successful music-making experiences. Her lessons were sequenced well and she directed children to do certain activities. However, she often offered student choices. By doing so, she empowered students and gave them a sense of ownership.

For example, in a first-grade lesson, the teacher taught the children to sing the song, *Rain on the Green Grass* (Gagne, 2009). She then asked them to choose how to move to the song, what movements to do for certain words, and finally what instruments to play on those certain words.

Sometimes, the teacher asked open-ended questions to allow students to generate ideas. The teacher asked kindergarteners how they could move to the song, *Raindrops, Raindrops* (Teacher Created Resources Staff, 2009). Students shared their ideas, and she guided them to settle on movements. The children sang with assigned gestures during that song, and were allowed to move freely during another song, *It's Raining, It's Pouring* (Gagne, 2001).

The teacher took cues from students and allowed their natural responses to affect the lesson's flow. In one kindergarten class, she began a warm-up that would lead to the singing game, *Old King Glory* (Amidon & Amidon, 1991). She chose a volunteer to be the leader. Before she could explain what to do, the child began walking around seated classmates. The teacher used the child's idea to introduce the movement for the song. She was surprised to see that the child's natural inclination worked well.

The teacher's methods reflect Orff-Schulwerk philosophy. She stated, “Positivity in your teaching style, discipline, and approach is the best way to get what you want out of your students...although it is not always the easiest thing to do. It is a ‘must’ for success.” She created classroom environments that made students feel safe to try ideas and voice their opinions. Because of this, it was not surprising to see spontaneity in children as they responded to her lessons.

Discussion

In evaluating rhythmic responses, the researcher found that kindergarteners were the only age

group that continued spontaneous musical behaviors during class “down-time.” They used mainly large muscle groups to show steady beats, whereas second graders used small muscle groups. This indicates that the complexity of performing beat and rhythm increases with children's ages.

A few kindergarteners and first graders spontaneously performed the rhythm of words or phrases of speech pieces and songs; one created an ostinato pattern. This suggests that some students in grades K-1 were ready to move past steady beat, and identify rhythms and ostinati in music. Some second graders exhibited their problem-solving skills by altering body percussion while performing an ostinato pattern.

Spontaneous melodic responses were less common among all three groups of children. Only one kindergartener sang an invented song spontaneously, which could be categorized as an imaginative song (Moog, 1976). The lack of spontaneous song behavior supported Barrett's (2006) study, where spontaneity was not valued when children were taught prescribed ways to sing when they entered elementary school around age seven.

In terms of spoken responses, kindergarteners and first graders discussed the elements of music that they heard (e.g., a rhythm pattern) or how the music sounded (e.g., like a hard rain). First-graders also improvised dialogue conversations with their peers, showing more advanced social interaction skills. Most kindergarteners and first graders used inventive language to discuss and describe the music; the music teacher did not perceive this behavior as misbehaving.

Kindergarteners and first-graders showed the most capacity under exploratory spontaneous responses. Kindergarten students stomped or wiggled like sea creatures as they entered and left the music classroom. First-graders dramatized their movements while exploring activities such as the rain movement and the set dance. This study did not support Sims's (1985) study; kindergarteners and first-graders in this study moved spontaneously more often than second-graders, showing a decline in exploratory movement as they aged.

Limitations

This study data emerged from a small number of children and only four observations over five weeks. The results did not reflect the general population. More observations over a longer period

of time may generate additional data that would allow an in-depth study of spontaneous responses among children in grades K–2.

Conclusion

If music teachers aim to develop independent musicians who are life-long music lovers, it is important to understand how children naturally respond. Music teachers affect students' spontaneous behaviors in

the music classroom. Being flexible is the key when teachers take cues from students and trust their ideas. By encouraging students' ideas and responses, teachers can promote positive and productive music classrooms. The Schulwerk's student-centered approach involves teaching processes that are rooted in children's musical play. Creating a classroom environment that is positive and safe is important for this playful spontaneity to occur. ■

REFERENCES

- Amidon, P., & Amidon, M. (Eds.). (1991). *Jump Jim Joe: Great singing games for children*. Brattleboro, VT: New England Dancing Masters.
- Barrett, M. (2006). Inventing songs, inventing worlds: The 'genesis' of creative thought and activity in young children's lives. *International Journal of Early Years Education*, 14(3), 201–220.
- Cambell, P. S. (2010). *Songs in their heads: Music and its meaning in children's lives* (2nd ed.). New York, NY: Oxford University Press.
- Curran, A. (2006). On spontaneous music. *Contemporary Music Review*, 25(5–6), 483–490.
- Emerson, R. M., Fretz, R. I., & Shaw, L. L. (1995). *Writing ethnographic fieldnotes*. Chicago, IL: The University of Chicago Press.
- Gagne, D. (2001). *The Orff source: 89 Orff arrangements of traditional folk songs and singing games*. Alberta, Canada: Themes & Variations.
- Gagne, D. (2009). *Singing games children love: PreK–grade 3* (Vol. 3). Alberta, Canada: Themes & Variations.
- Leedy, P. D., & Ormrod, J. E. (Eds.). (2013). *Practical research: Planning and design* (3rd ed.). New York, NY: Pearson.
- Mead, V. H. (1996). More than mere movement. *Music Educators Journal*, 82(4), 38–41.
- Merriam-Webster. (2012). Dictionary. Retrieved from: <http://www.merriamwebster.com/> Accessed April 20, 2012.
- Moog, H. (1976). *The musical experience of the pre-school child*. (C. Clarke, Trans.). London: Schott. (Original work published 1968)
- Shamrock, M. (1997). Orff-Schulwerk: An integrated foundation. *Music Educators Journal*, 83(6), 41–44.
- Sims, W. (1985). Young children's creative movement to music: Categories of movement, rhythmic characteristics, and reactions to change. *Contributions to Music Education*, 12, 42–50.
- Teacher Created Resources Staff. (2009). *Year round poetry for young learners*. Westminster, CA: Teacher Created Resources.
- Young, S. (2002). Young children's spontaneous vocalizations in free-play: Observations of two- to three-year-olds in day-care settings. *Bulletin of the Council for Research in Music Education*, 152, 43–53.